

USING LANGUAGE AND CULTURAL MEDIATION TO IMPROVE LEARNING

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Annotation:When learning a language for cross-cultural communication, mediation serves as both a means of learning and an end in itself. The goal of learning a language is to enable students to comprehend and consider how meaning is made and interpreted, to engage with the variety of meanings found in communication acts, and then to react to these meanings in their interactions with other people. Through the mediation process, learners get an understanding of how to make meaning and interpret it by seeing the actions of more experienced individuals. This duality adds complexity to our understanding of the nature of mediation in language learning, which calls for a more nuanced understanding of mediation and must be recognized and addressed in study and instruction.

Keywords:integration, media ,target, mutual, instruction, incorporation, retention, selection, application

1.Introduction

In its most expansive definition, "to mediate" refers to mediating a dispute between parties in order to assist in reaching a consensus. This type of "mediation" frequently takes place in domestic as well as political and industrial disagreements, for instance. In the context of language use, "mediation" has taken on a related and equally significant meaning: helping people deal with situations or ideas that are unfamiliar to them, speak different languages, or have trouble understanding certain terms or concepts. This kind of mediation is summarised in the [Common European Framework of Reference for Languages](#) as follows: "... the written and/or oral activities of mediation make communication possible between persons who are unable, for whatever reason, to communicate with each other directly. Translation or interpretation, a paraphrase, summary or record, provides for a third party a (re)formulation of a [spoken or written] source text to which this third party does not have direct access. Mediating language activities – (re)processing an existing text – occupy an important place in the normal linguistic functioning of our societies"¹. Lack of proficiency in the other language or register (for instance, between speakers of different languages or between experts and non-experts in a particular field); cognitive gaps, or unfamiliarity with certain concepts or processes (e.g., due to limited access to education, low literacy, or cognitive development); a lack of pertinent information (e.g., regarding how to apply for housing); cultural differences (e.g., relating to concepts of politeness or punctuality); or disability. These are undoubtedly circumstances that migrants entering or relocating to a new host nation are likely to face. Therefore, mediation is crucial for them as well as for everyone unfamiliar with a nation, its language, and its culture.

Mediation as a concept has found increasing space in research on language teaching and learning and is an emerging part of the theoretical apparatus of researchers in the field. It has become particularly significant in interculturally oriented thinking about teaching and learning a language. However, it is a complex concept and thinking it and its relevance for language learning has developed in different and at times in seemingly contradictory ways. The concept of mediation into thinking about language teaching and learning and the explore some of the issues that emerge from this work. In particular, it will consider the ways in which mediation is understood and the multiple uses that the term has in the language education literature and seek to identify the common elements that underlie these multiple uses. It will begin by examining the concept in Byram's work and then examine the ways that this idea has been elaborated in other contexts before proposing a synthesis of thinking about the concept.

Swiss linguist Ferdinand De Saussure has revolutionized linguistic thought when he introduced structuralist ideas on how mutual understanding by means of language is supposed to work. Later, even

¹ Council of Europe (2001): *Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment* (CEFR), CUP, Cambridge. Available on line at www.coe.int/lang-CEFR.

philosophers showed considerable interest in his thoughts and they paved the way for cultural philosophy and the integration of culture into social theory . Linguists doing research on intercultural communication on that basis, on the one hand, found a first solid basis to integrate culture into linguistic theory. On the other hand, after the era of structuralism, the assumed constraints of this paradigm tended to persist in linguistics and for a long time they impeded linguists from taking note of the advances of cultural theory after structuralism.

Meanwhile, the notion of culture has turned into a popular way to link macro-social phenomena to micro-social observation in the social sciences. Besides of that, authors from cross-cultural and intercultural research continue to point at today's enormous increase of cross-cultural exchange and interact. Linguists from different schools continue to claim a priority role for linguistic approaches in cross-cultural and intercultural communication research. In these respects, they point at the fact that intercultural interaction will always and necessarily be carried out by means of (verbal) communication and that consequently, empirical methods from linguistics will tend to provide the most valuable insights.

Since culture had never had its own place in classical linguistic theory, linguists got used to borrow notions and definitions on what culture was supposed to be from other academic disciplines. As a consequence, linguists today have a wide choice of concepts of culture at their disposal. This variety may on the one hand enrich the potential of linguistic research. On the other hand it should be kept in mind that, although many authors would reject this for their research, one of the main motivations for doing research on intercultural communication might still be seen in the mission to find ways to improve people's intercultural competence. From this point of view, culture is seen as a variable that will on the one hand influence the outcome of people's interaction, but that on the other hand may be actively used by interact ants to improve their outcomes in terms of mutual understanding and/or agreement.[1]

Byram's work has been a significant point of departure for thinking about the idea of mediation and the concept has evolved over time in Byram's work. The term 'mediation' is introduced in Byram as a relatively marginal idea drawn from Bochner . Bochner identified four possible outcomes of intercultural contact, one of which he called 'mediating' persons, which he describes as People who have the ability to act as links between different cultural systems, bridging the gap by introducing, translating, representing and reconciling cultures to each other. [5] The mediator is thus someone who connects cultures, and this idea has remained central to Bryam's thinking about mediation. Byram argues that developing such mediating persons should be the normal goal for language education, and while he explores what the development of such persons may entail, he does not do so in terms of developing an understanding of mediation itself. The idea of mediation is taken up in Buttjes and Byram.[7] The main contribution about mediation in this work comes from Buttjes, and Byram himself does not use the term mediation in his chapter. Buttjes discusses mediation through the lens of language acquisition comparing the acquisition processes for first and foreign languages and arguing that in first language acquisition, language is used to mediate culture but this is substantially lacking in second language acquisition. Although he does not actually define mediation, he does associate it with the relativisation of learners' cultures, critical comparisons between cultures and negotiation of meaning. Thus, he views mediation as a process through which learners are brought into cultures. The chapters in the book, including Byram's, connect with this underlying idea, but overall, there is little discussion of what actually constitutes mediation. In this early work, mediation is present but not developed in a substantive way. The main development of the idea in Byram's work begins with his collaboration with Zarate and their conceptualisation of the intercultural speaker. They argued that acting interculturally involved bringing two cultures into relationship and that one of the things that language education should develop is the ability to see how different cultures relate to each other, and to act as mediators between them [14].

3.Results and discussion

Traditional Methods of Teaching Culture Improved with Technology

The more traditional methods and approaches to teaching culture, such as movies and video, can be enhanced through the integration of digital media. Feature films have become readily available and have been included in numerous textbooks and designed to actively involve the learner. Foreign language

instructors are beginning to incorporate more movies in the FL classroom as “an accessible window” to the target culture through “combined effects of images, sounds, camera, plots and dialogue”. Media literacy promotes cross-cultural competence and comprehension focused on meaning rather than on form, as well as repeated exposure to L2 cultural products, practices, and perspectives, and the target language itself.

Technology has changed the nature of instruction and learning. Teachers are exploring digital technologies to make learning more effective and engage students actively. Technology promotes socially active language in multiple authentic contexts due to its “accessibility, flexibility, connectivity speed and independence of methodological approach”. It gives foreign language teachers various opportunities to create better and more effective instructional materials to teach not only the language structure, but also the target culture. Students can take advantage of technology by learning in formal and informal settings through interactive social spaces. Technological devices such as smart phones, laptops and computers, PDAs, etc., as well as Web 2.0 technologies are widely used to support student learning in a classroom setting, and they have opened new vistas for language learning and teaching in particular. One of the alluring benefits of technology is that it provides authentic communication in an interactive environment that facilitates the teaching of culture. Through the use of interactive media, students become less dependent on the printed word and more engaged with authentic cultural content they can access and explore freely, because they have more control of the selection and application of materials and resources. These numerous resources and materials allow teachers to tailor digital media to make culture learning more relevant and accessible to the students in their classroom. With the incorporation of technology, both the teacher and the students become part of the interactive environment. Technology creates an “open-ended” learning environment in which the results are not predetermined. [2]

2. Conclusion

More importantly, with interactive web resources that provide the benefits of networking and real time communication, the students can continue to learn the target language and enhance their cultural understanding outside the classroom .Technology permits both teachers and students “to go beyond quick and superficial stops on the information highway and establish meaningful interactive learning scenarios”. A number of researchers have investigated the use of technology in an L2 classroom. For instance, Levy describes technologies that can be used in a foreign language classroom in relation to skills, including grammar, vocabulary, reading, writing, pronunciation, listening, speaking, and culture. Levy suggests that “simply accessing an L2 Web site can expose learners to numerous aspects of the target culture”. However, when exploring the websites, learners are engaged passively, which may result in low retention. Similar results were found in Moore’s study, in which it was concluded that the majority of classroom students simply “surf the net” rather than being engaged in the learning. On the other hand, only a few teachers indicated that they use Internet for meaningful activities. [3]

Teachers find blogs attractive for at least two reasons—interactivity and collaboration . Blogs promote reading and writing, knowledge sharing, feedback and reflection, as well as cultural learning. By reading blogs written by native speakers, students can gain cultural understanding of different perspectives of L2 native speakers .There are a number of freely available blog publishing tools, such as Live Journal, Edu blogs, Blogger, etc., that can be adapted in a foreign language classroom. Blogs are powerful vehicles for self- expression and self-empowerment.

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